

QUIZ**LAST NAME: KA'ANA'ANA****FIRST NAME: CARMEN****PROGRAM CODE: LLM****COURSE CODE : ACA-401****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (footnotes).

The author used Zotero to insert references.

The author used the following software: MS Office on Windows 10

QUIZ: A SUMMATIVE ASSESSMENT

1. **What is not an example of a logical flow connector?**

- Therefore.
- As an example.
- On the other hand.
- And so forth.¹**

2. **Which sentence correctly uses an apostrophe to indicate possession?**

¹*EUCLID Period 6 Video*, 2:55, accessed March 16, 2020, <https://eucliduniversity.net/periods/aca-401-period-6/>.

- The United States's laws mandate death for treason.**²
- The United States' law mandate death for treason.
- The United State's law mandate death for treason.
- The United State law's mandate death for treason.
3. **American influence has grown world-wide including American English, three of the following are reasons cited as contributing to American English being the dominant influence on World English, which is not a reason?**
- The international political and economic position of the U.S.
- The 15 global territories of the United States.**³
- The magnitude of global mass media and media technology influence.
- The appeal of American popular culture on language and habits.
4. **Bear is to sleuth like:**
- Sherlock Holmes is to detective.
- Tigress is to stalk.
- Vixen is to skulk.**⁴
- Nanny is to kid.

² Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401 Coursepack for Period 1*, 2nd ed. (Bangui, Central African Republic: Euclid University, 2019), 18.

³ Cleenewerck and Gulma, 27.

⁴ Dave Kemper, Verne Meyer, and Patrick Sebranek, *Write Source 2000: A Guide to Writing, Thinking and Learning* (Wilmington, Massachusetts: Great Source Education Group, 1999), 465.

5. **What does a bar graph not show?**
- How things change over time.**⁵
 - How different things compare to one another.
 - A snapshot comparison of one point in time.
 - A stacked comparison of parts with the bars.
6. **Anthropomorphism, or personification, is an error to avoid in research writing. Which of the following is not an example of anthropomorphism?**
- eBooks teach timeless wisdom.
 - The internet gives answers to all questions.
 - Records tell us that internet use is on the rise.
 - Internet users record more hours logged online.**⁶
7. **Which is a correct Turabian style citation for sacred works?**

⁵ Kemper, Meyer, and Sebranek, 303.

⁶ EUCLID, *ACA-401 Coursepack for Period 4* (Washington DC: Euclid University Press, 2015), 16.

- “You are not to covet... anything that belongs to your neighbor.” **Romans 13:9 (International Standard Version).**⁷
- “You are not to steal”, Exodus 20:15 (International Standard Version).
- “You are not to steal or lie or deal falsely with your neighbor.” *Leviticus* 19:11 (ISV).
- “If that person has sinned and has been found guilty, then he is to return the stolen thing that he took” Leviticus 6:4 (ISV).

8. **Which is a correct Turabian style citation for works of art?**

- Leonardo Da Vinci. The Mona Lisa, ca. 1517, The Louvre Museum, Paris.
- Leonardo Da Vinci, *The Mona Lisa*, ca. 1517, The Louvre Museum, Paris.**⁸
- Leonardo Da Vinci, The Mona Lisa, ca. 1517, *The Louvre Museum*, Paris.
- Leonardo Da Vinci, *The Mona Lisa*, ca. 1517, The Louvre Museum, Paris.

9. **Which is correct for *The Bluebook* style of citation of numerals and symbols?**

- 4,800 people paid \$64.8 billion into Bernie Madoff's pyramid scheme.

⁷ Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations, Ninth Edition: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, Edition 9 (The University of Chicago Press, 2018), 114.

⁸ Turabian, 119.

- 4,800 people paid sixty-four point eight billion dollars into Bernie Madoff's pyramid scheme.
- Four thousand eight hundred people paid \$64.8 billion into Bernie Madoff's pyramid scheme.⁹**
- Four thousand eight hundred people paid sixty-four point eight billion dollars into Bernie Madoff's pyramid scheme.

10. Which is correct for *The Bluebook* style of citation of foreign words and phrases?

- Hawaiian words are commonly used around the world, bringing the world closer together as one ohana, one family: *aloha*, *hula*, *lei*, *ahi*, *mahi-mahi*, “big” *kahuna*, and *wiki(pedia)* are just a few.
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⁹ Columbia Law Review Ass'n et al. eds., *The Bluebook: A Uniform System of Citation, 20th Edition* (Cambridge, MA: The Harvard Law Review Association, 2010), 81.

¹⁰ Columbia Law Review Ass'n et al. eds., 83.

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